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HOW THE MIND CAN BE TRAINED TO PERFORM AT PEAK LEVEL DURING ELITE SPORTING COMPETITIONS ESPECIALLY WHEN FACING ADVERSITY

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Abstract. In this work, we propose a brief analysis of techniques and methods for improvement of sportsmen's mental state. The accent is made on such techniques as Visualization, Breathing with Clear Mind and Heart Rate Variability. We also consider the importance of rest for the brain and nervous system and the ways to handle anxiety and fear. And, in the final part of our research, we make general recommendations for athletes how they can improve their mental state by working with different techniques.

Keywords: mental state, adversity, breathing, visualization, heart rate variability.

Introduction. Many sportsmen, coaches and sports science specialists believe in the power of Mind and that it can be trained to achieve peak performance during adverse and critical circumstances. At the same time, there is a lack of information about strategies and methods which can be used for this purpose. There is a necessity to have a brief and informative set of rules and recommendations that can be effectively used for improving the psychological possibilities of the sportsmen [1, 2].

In this paper, we will try to answer the question: How the mind can be trained to perform at peak level during Elite Sporting Competitions especially when facing adversity?

Objective: The main goal of this paper is to explain to sportsmen and coaches how they can improve their psychological preparedness in order to win medals at Olympics & other premier Sporting Events on a consistent basis.

Results of the research. Based on our experience we propose 3 techniques for improvement of the sportsmen's mental state: Visualization, Breathing with Clear Mind and Heart Rate Variability.

Visualization: It creates a blueprint in mind with rehearsal by repeating mental practice. Movement is automatic and easy to recall. Visualization works as it produces small muscle contractions as if you are actually playing the sport.

If we rehearse often and with intensity, we strengthen the muscle firing; so, the same is recalled efficiently during competition. It creates muscle memory similar to the actual practice on field which is apparent when some young boys and girls excel in some sports when they watch the game with a lot of interest on various Media.

It helps in at least 3 ways:

- Assists in reducing actual practice time on the ground thus conserving body & managing fatigue.
- Correct errors during visualization thus learning faster on the ground.

- Improves longevity in sport and minimizes burnouts due to improved utilization of resources.

Breathing with Clear Mind: Probably it's the most important aspect of staying focused in Sport.

- Proper breathing – Oxygenates Blood & energizes brain, nerves & muscles.
- Short shallow breaths from Upper Chest restrict muscles – Breathing stressed, inefficient & causes fatigue – physical & mental.
- In contrast, deep breathing – Destressing & efficient.
- Also, over arousal leads to shallow breaths & causes muscle tension & cramps.
- Breathing exercises – several times a day so you remember during the Match/Event.

Heart Rate Variability: By using Heart Rate Scanners and analyzing Data, it provides insight into the focus and attention of an athlete both on ground and off ground.

In the second part of our research, we propose recommendations for athletes how to use Rest Periods and how to handle anxiety and fear.

It's well known that the left part of human brain is responsible for strategic planning, while the right part – for execution of commands.

Just before commencement of action, seamless shift of action from left to right associated with faster reaction times, motor/ technical control & better outcomes.

If there is nervous & muscle tension, it disrupts the shift of action from left to right part of the brain & it renders Athlete incapable of Peak motor or technical ability.

Rest Period: An overtrained athlete is a fatigued athlete and usually does not perform at peak level in competition as fatigue sets in affecting athletes mentally and physically due to anxiety and creeping fear.

All elite Sportspersons must be mentored/supported on the importance of rest period. The rest day is the most important day of the week as it assists body to rejuvenate and get energized/ ready for next week.

It also enables time to catch up with family/friends as they are the permanent support system for athletes. It allows mind to review the performance of the past week and refocus for the coming week including work on equipment etc. if required. Though, it is important to enjoy

your rest day in moderation, but same time ensure not to binge on food/alcohol and waste an entire week's good work.

Closer to competition, several athletes put in longer hours. It is important to train on a consistent basis throughout the year rather than large variations near the competition. Athletes must learn to listen to their bodies and act accordingly. They must find out what works for them and what doesn't which is possible if you follow **LTO Mantra – Listen, Think and Observe**.

Anxiety and Handling fear:

The most common query is how to handle anxiety and fear of losing. We can never do away with them but learn to manage them and use them to advantage to outperform during competition. Parents and coaches play a crucial part – unconditional support required no matter what happens.

If the athlete practiced well, achieved higher fitness levels, performed well during the match, and still lost, learn to accept the loss, and return with better preparation next time. He should always analyze both wins and losses and work on them – wins to reinforce what he is doing well and losses to work on weaknesses in his game. Practice moderation when he wins and it's alright to feel bad when he loses but ensure himself that next day, early morning, he will be back on the field doing his best.

The athlete should believe and have faith in his instincts as he has prepared and practiced for this day. He shouldn't overthink while competing, he should walk away from negative thoughts. It's alright to have butterflies in the stomach but should not induce fear where it affects performance in a negative way on the field.

And in the third part of our research, we propose recommendations of a general character that are supposed to help athletes to improve their mental state.

Performance-oriented Goals vs. Outcome-oriented Goals: Athletes should always focus on performance rather than winning – Practice, Fitness, and work on Mental strength – to reduce the gap between practice and real match play.

They should practice under difficult weather conditions to be mentally and physically ready for any challenge.

Create pressure situations during practice - always practice with high intensity like real match situations and play matches like serious practice – to reduce the difference in stress levels during real match situations so we are fairly used to raised stress levels.

They should always take calculated risks – may lose initially but would start performing consistently sooner than later.

Be assertive with controlled aggression on the Sporting arena.

Work on things under their control: Practise hours, mental and physical fitness regimes, time management, equipment etc. Do not worry about things like weather conditions, Crowd, referees, poor line calls and poor surface which are beyond their control.

This will prevent better performance in the future too as the mind is always ready to offer lame excuses for poor performances.

Enjoy Pressure Situations: If the sportsman wants to win more often, then he should learn to enjoy pressure situations in sport. Start using keywords or lines. Tell himself that “It's a difficult situation but I am still enjoying it” or “I will find ways to overcome this situation”.

The idea is to identify, acknowledge and face the pressure situation and not to run away from it. Deep breath, slow down and re-strategize if required to come out of difficult situations.

Learn to let go: Unforced errors – Forgive himself verbally and move on. Bring Focus on what lies ahead. Tell himself – “I will try not to repeat this stupid mistake and move on”.

Do not lower his guard at any time in a Match even if he is winning easily.

Try to finish Matches as early as possible as it helps conserve body resources for future Matches.

Create a Sporting Ecosystem around them: Elite Sportspersons must create a Team around them who will assist the Athlete in achieving Sporting excellence.

As soon as there is an understanding that there is a special Sporting talent in you and you are serious about having a professional career in Sports, try and have a Team of three – a Coach, Fitness Trainer and Mental Trainer with you.

Change if required unless you find the right combination/ Team.

As you grow in your Sport, you must add Physiotherapist, Nutritionist, Sport Scientist, Data Analyst, etc. to the Team who will take you far at World/ Olympics level.

The State Sports/ Olympics Federations must assist deserving Athletes with finances and Team support required.

Conclusion

It's obvious, that success in sports depends both on the physical and psychological preparedness of the athletes. Each sportsman should find his own optimal strategy how to combine physical and psychological methods. Coaches also should teach the sportsmen how they should train their minds using the methods presented in this paper.

We will end with a Quote from the Star Trek series telecast in 1990s on TV: **“Mental game of sport is the final frontier to gain that elusive competitive edge.”**

References:

1. Mental Training for Peak Performance by Steven Ungerleider, 2005, 272 pp.
2. Evidence based Applied Sport Psychology by Roland A. Carlstedt, 2012, 528 pp.